

Bias and Entropy Part II

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In Part I, we argued that one may find the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution by removing bias for two body elastic collisions. We explicitly made use of two equations: $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4 = E_1$ and $f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_3)f(e_4)$, which implies independence of f 's and a lack of bias for E_1 . Here $f(e_i)$ is the probability to have a single particle energy of e_i . We used the idea of independence to obtain an equation for $f(e_1)$ alone which is of the same form as a maximization of entropy for a gas, using Shannon's entropy, subject to the constraint $\sum_i e_i f(e_i) = E$.

Here, we obtain $f(e_i) = A \exp(-e_i/T)$ in a different manner using infinitesimal changes in E_1 in $C(E_1)$ where $\ln(C(E_1)) = \ln(f(e_i)) + \ln(f(e_j))$ for $e_i + e_j = E_1$. One may change either e_1 or e_2 in order to change E_1 and this leads to the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution.

We next consider the idea of non-bias in a gas of N particles and total energy E . The $f(e_i)$ certainly contain bias, but this is expected because they represent different e_i values. We suggest that if e_i describes the entire bias of $f(e_i)$, then there is no extra bias based on anything else. We consider picking N_1 particles ($N_1 \rightarrow$ infinite) from an MB gas. This leads to the product probability $\text{Product over } i f(e_i)$ power $(N_1 f(e_i))$ for the large N_1 case. Taking \ln yields: $\sum_i f(e_i) \ln(f(e_i)) + \text{constants}$. There exists a second equation: $\sum_i e_i f(e_i) = E$. We suggest that bias based only e implies that: $f(e_i) \ln(f(e_i)) = e f(e_i)$. This lack of bias is mathematically equivalent to maximizing a function $-\sum_i f(e_i) \ln(f(e_i))$ subject to the constraint $\sum_i e_i f(e_i)$. This result is equivalent to the no bias approach for $f(e_i)f(e_j)$ and even in the N run sample is also equivalent to no bias at its root. Thus, we suggest that the maximization of entropy follows formally from a lack of bias.

Lack of Bias in Two Body Collisions

We suggest that in a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas, one should seek a lack of bias for the physical elastic two-body collisions. This suggests that for $e_i + e_j = E_1$:

$$f(e_i)f(e_j) = C(E_1) = \text{constant for } E_1 \quad ((1))$$

If there were bias, certain i, j pairs would be preferred over others even though E_1 is the same for all.

To solve ((1)), we suggest considering: $E_1 \rightarrow E_1 + d$, where d is infinitesimal. We then consider the two cases, $e_i \rightarrow e_i + d$ and $e_j \rightarrow e_j + d$ separately.

$$dC/dE \text{ at } E_1 = d \ln(f(e)) / de \text{ at } e_i \text{ or } e_j \quad ((2))$$

Thus: $d \ln(f(e)) / de = \text{constant}$. Calling $\text{constant} = -1/T$ yields: $f(e) = C \exp(-e/T)$ ((3)).

This is the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution.

Lack of Bias in a Maxwell-Boltzmann Gas

Imagine that one does not wish to focus on a lack of bias in two-body collisions, but wishes to see bias directly in a gas of N particles with a total energy E in another way. Where is this lack of bias? It cannot be in $f(e_i)$ because this equals $\exp(-e_i/T)$ as seen above. We suggest that the $f(e_i)$ differ in value because they are linked to the information e_i . There is thus a certain amount of bias. We suggest then that there should be no further bias, but such a statement must be quantified.

We suggest considering picking N_1 particles ($N_1 \rightarrow \text{infinite}$) out of the gas, one at a time. The probability for a particular run is:

$$\text{Probability of a run} = \text{Product over } i \text{ } f(e_i)^{N_1} \text{ for the large } N_1 \text{ case} \quad ((4))$$

$$\ln(\text{Probability of a run}) = \text{Sum over } i \text{ } f(e_i) \ln(f(e_i)) + \text{constant} \quad ((5))$$

This probability contains various $f(e_i) \ln(f(e_i))$ terms and is somewhat similar in appearance to:

$$E/N = \text{Sum over } i \text{ } e_i f(i) \quad ((6))$$

In ((6)) $e_i f(i)$ is the bias associated with $f(e_i)$. We suggest that if there is no further bias than this in the problem, $\ln(f(e_i)) = -e_i/T$. If it does not, then there is further bias in the problem.

This suggestion is mathematically equivalent to maximizing $-\text{Sum over } i \text{ } f(e_i) \ln(f(e_i))$ subject to the constraint $\text{Sum over } i \text{ } e_i f(e_i) = E$, but we argue that essentially one wishes $\ln(f(e_i))$ to have the same value as $-e_i/T$ in order that there be no extra bias.

The result from the removal of bias in $f(e_i)f(e_j)$ where $e_i+e_j=E$, yields the same result. Thus, a lack of bias in the product probability is also linked with a lack of bias in an MB gas, but one has to use the special function $-\text{Sum over } i \text{ } f(e_i) \ln(f(e_i))$ in that case.

If there is no bias in picking particles out one at a time, one might expect that a lack of bias is already present in the two body collisions. A bias in one place (beyond the information e_i bias) seems to imply a bias in the other, but it is good specifically check that the two lack of bias approaches yield the same distribution which they do.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we suggest that one may consider independence and a lack of bias in two-body collisions in a gas to write: $f(e_i)f(e_j) = C(E)$ where $e_i+e_j=E$ and $C(E)$ is a particular constant pertaining to E . Using $C(E+d)$ and writing two equations, one with $f(e_i+d)$ and the other with $f(e_j+d)$, yields: $d/de \ln(f(e)) = \text{constant}$ if d is infinitesimal. Setting $\text{constant} = -1/T$ yields the Maxwell-Boltzmann result: $f(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$.

It is possible that one does not wish to examine a lack of bias in two body collisions, but rather a lack of bias in a gas. One might consider picking particles out one at a time and computing the probability of a large N_1 run. This yields: $\ln(\text{Probability}) = \text{Sum over } i \text{ } f(e_i) \ln(f(e_i)) + \text{constant}$. A

second equation exists, namely that for the entire gas: $\sum_i f(e_i) e_i = E/N$. If $f(e_i)e_i$ is the only bias associated with $f(e_i)$, one might suggest that $f(e_i)\ln(f(e_i))$ and $e_i f(e_i)$ should be equivalent, i.e. $\ln(f(e_i)) = e_i$ constant. If this is not the case, it seems to imply that there exists an additional bias to the e_i information one. This approach is equivalent to mathematically maximizing: $-\sum_i f(e_i) \ln(f(e_i))$ subject to the constraint $\sum_i e_i f(e_i) = E/N$. It also yields the same result as the removal of bias from a product probability used in two body collisions. In other words, seeking a lack of bias in both cases leads to the same result.